

DEVELOPMENT OF READING AND LISTENING SKILLS OF STUDENTS OF THE MEDICAL DIRECTION IN THE STUDY OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract This article emphasizes the importance of listening as speaking. Being a good listener can help solve problems, resolve conflicts, and improve relationships. Effective listening at work can help you make fewer mistakes, spend less time, and improve accuracy. The fact that effective listening helps build friendships and careers is a special insistence.

Key words: Listening, reading, fewer mistakes, classroom coursework, Personalize the content, importance of listening.

Аннотация В этой статье подчеркивается важность слушания так же, как и говорения. Умение хорошо слушать может помочь решать проблемы, разрешать конфликты и улучшать отношения. Эффективное прослушивание на работе может помочь вам совершать меньше ошибок, тратить меньше времени и повысить точность. Особое внимание уделяется тому факту, что эффективное слушание помогает строить дружеские отношения и карьеру.

Ключевые слова: аудирование, чтение, меньше ошибок, аудиторная курсовая работа, персонализация содержания, важность аудирования.

How can you ensure your students understand classroom coursework? Build reading skills. Teachers love to share their favorite stories and the subjects they are passionate about, but helping a child develop the same interest requires foundational reading skills to comprehend and enjoy the curriculum.

Reading skills are abilities that pertain to a person's capacity to read, comprehend, interpret and decode written language and texts. Exceptional reading skills can be highly beneficial to assimilating and responding to written communications like emails, messages, letters and other written messages. Using reading skills in the workplace can also be important for ensuring effective written communication, which can result in less miscommunication or misunderstanding of expectations.

Reading skills can also encompass several key aspects that work together to develop overall literacy skills, including comprehension, fluency, vocabulary and strategies that help readers interpret and find meaning in texts

Many children see reading as a chore, especially if it's tied to lesson plans and learning complex information. Teachers, parents and mentors can help ignite a child's passion to read by incorporating activities focused on building reading skills to improve comprehension and engagement. Decoding is a skill that relies on your ability to sound out words you've heard but never seen written out. It relies on phonemic awareness, which is the ability to hear individual sounds in words and connect those sounds to letters. Making the connection between a letter or group of letters the sounds they make and is a crucial step to "sounding out" or decoding words. Fluency refers to a mix of different factors. First, it focuses on your

ability to read clearly with flow. Fluency also focuses on your ability to decode new vocabulary quickly while reading. Fluency is what it sounds like to read, which can directly impact your ability to comprehend what you read. For example, as a child becomes more fluent in their reading, they will be able to quickly find meaning and an understanding of what they read, which contributes to understanding the text.

The ability to decode or determine the meaning of new words can also influence your reading comprehension. When you can quickly interpret new meanings and identify relationships between new vocabulary and familiar terms, you can increase your ability to make assumptions, form ideas and generally better understand the texts you read. Here are some simple and effective ways to help students build reading skills to better understand classroom curriculum.

1. Annotate and highlight text

Teach your students to highlight and underline valuable information as they read. Have students write notes on the pages they are reading to help them stay focused and improve comprehension. Students can also write down questions as they read to receive more explanation on a new concept or to define a new word.

2. Personalize the content

Students can increase their understanding by seeing how the material connects with their life. Have your students make personal connections with the text by writing it down on the page. You can also help students comprehend the text by helping them see an association with current events.

3. Practice problem solving skills

Blend real-world problem solving skills into your curriculum. Have your students write out solutions to the problem and discuss their ideas as a class or in small groups.

4. Incorporate more senses

Add in activities that reinforce learning and comprehension by using more senses as they read. Remind students to read with a pen or pencil to annotate the text. Have your students take turns reading out loud. Use projectors to guide your lesson and write down questions for those who are visual learners.

5. Understand common themes

Ask your students to look for examples of a certain theme throughout the chapter to increase engagement. Have students share their findings with the class to help students learn a specific theme more in-depth.

6. Set reading goals

Have each student set their own reading goals. This can help them take action in building reading skills and students will be more mindful of how they are improving.

7. Read in portions

Long, complex reading can be more digestible by breaking it up into pieces. Shorter segments will help students retain the information as the class discusses the materials. It can also help students build confidence in understanding a complex subject.

8. Let students guide their reading

Your students process reading material and curriculum in very different ways. As you implement reading activities to help your class learn complex materials, you will learn what works best for each student individually.

Having effective listening skills means being able to display interest in the topic discussed and understand the information provided. In today's society, the ability to communicate effectively is becoming increasingly important. Although the ability to speak effectively is a highly sought-after skill, developing effective listening skills is often not regarded in the same respect.

Five ways to improve your listening skills

1. Face the speaker and give them your attention

It is difficult to talk to someone who is constantly looking around. Make sure to face the speaker, maintain eye contact, and give them your undivided attention. In Western cultures, eye contact is necessary for effective communication. Although shyness, uncertainty, or cultural taboos may inhibit eye contact, try your best to make sure the speaker knows that they have your full attention.

2. Keep an open mind

Do not judge or mentally criticize what the speaker is telling you. Doing so can compromise your ability to take in what is being said. Never exhibit judgmental behavior, as it compromises your effectiveness as a listener. You can evaluate what was said after the speaker is finished talking, but don't do so while you are still listening to them.

Let the speaker finish what they are saying and don't be a sentence-grabber. Interrupting the speaker or prohibiting them from finishing what they are saying can indicate disrespect to the speaker. Often, interrupting the speaker mid-sentence interrupts their train of thought and can easily destroy a productive conversation.

3. Active listening

Active listening shows the speaker that you're interested and is an important business communication skill. Using active listening techniques helps to ensure that you correctly understand what is said.

Active listening techniques:

Paraphrasing back to the speaker what was said, to show understanding

Nonverbal cues (nodding, eye contact, etc.)

Verbal affirmations ("I understand," "I know," "Thank you," etc.)

Demonstrating concern and establishing rapport

4. Just listen!

Create a mental model of the information, whether it be a picture or an arrangement of abstract concepts. Listen to keywords and phrases and do not rehearse what you are going to say after the speaker is done talking. Think about what the other person is saying rather than what you are going to respond with. It is difficult to think of what you are going to say while also listening to the speaker. Be attentive and relaxed – don't get distracted by your own thoughts and feelings.

As teachers implement more reading activities into classroom coursework, students will find improvement in vocabulary, writing skills, problem solving, concentration, and cognitive development to help build a solid foundation for future learning.

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